

CONCEPT FOR SUPPORTING THE DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHER EDUCATION FOR THE PERIOD

Khodjaeva Guzal Djahonobodovna

Senior teacher, Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Fergana, Uzbekistan

E-mail: guzalhodzaeva26@gmail.com

Annotation: The article determines the importance of the technological approach in the process of teaching literature at school. Considering the models of a modern teacher available in didactics, the authors determine the use of pedagogical technologies as the most important component of professional teacher competence. Studying in detail the concept of “pedagogical technology”, the authors identify its features based on comparison with methodology, defend their own opinion in a discussion on the issue of technologization of literature as an educational subject, characterize the program for the use of technology in educational activities.

Keywords: Pedagogical technologies, professional competence, theory activity-based learning, model of teacher-technologist.

Introduction

"Changing the content of teacher training programs and teaching technologies in order to ensure the implementation of a new professional standard for teachers and new standards of school education" is one of the primary responsibilities up until 2015. One may say that the modernization of Russian education involves major inventive changes, the most important of which being the prioritization of technological advancements in the educational process. The renewal of Russian education is centered on the implementation of efficient methods for guaranteeing its quality. The use of pedagogical technologies enhances teaching practice by fostering the development of new procedural skills, the ability to handle information, and innovative solutions to scientific problems with an emphasis on program individualization and learning environment differentiation, according to an analysis of the effectiveness of training [1-4].

The notion of "technology for education"

"Pedagogical technology is an integrated model of educational activities designed with meticulous attention to detail for the purpose of organizing, planning,

and executing the learning process while guaranteeing teachers and students have comfortable surroundings to work in." "The goal of pedagogical technology is the optimization of educational forms through a systematic approach to developing, implementing, and characterizing the entire process of teaching and learning knowledge while accounting for technical and human resources and their interactions." Organization of Eastern Africa Yet, M.V. Clarina defines "pedagogical technology" as "a systemic set and order of functioning of all personal, instrumental, and methodological means used to achieve pedagogical goals," regardless of the sense-forming components that support this idea. A framework proposed by G.K. Seleuko that comprises the following invariant elements is reflected in the understanding of pedagogical technology as a set of goals, content, forms, means, procedures, and processes necessary for a structured and intentional impact on the child's personality:

Educational technologies, like any innovations or changes, are applied at three interconnected levels, according to an analysis of educational practice: - general didactic (general pedagogical), which describes the entire educational process; - private methodological (specific subject), which enables the implementation of Pedagogical technologies within a single subject; - local (modular), exemplified by the technologies of specific learning modules [5-9].

Technology and approach used in education

The primary technological criteria were developed in Yu.K. Babansky's laboratory in the 1970s, but the terms "pedagogical technology" and "teaching methods," particularly at the local and individual subject levels, are frequently confused. The main distinction between the two is where the emphasis is placed. "solving didactic problems with precisely defined goals, each of which needs to have a clear description and definition in order to be achieved."

The goal-setting approach that pedagogical technology provides is marked by greater instrumentality, according to M.M. Potashnik's writings. According to didactics, objectives should be testable and repeatable in order to be considered diagnostic [10-13]. Any pedagogical technology is characterized by its reproducibility, stability of results, lack of many "ifs," and certain "rigidity," which is the opposite of an intentional educational process that guarantees the ultimate result. Indicators of educational technologies, as emphasized by both foreign and local writers (e.g., B.S. Bloom, M.V. Clarin, G.K. Selevko, V.P. Bespalko, etc.),

also relate to the categories of reproducibility and diagnosticity: The achievement of goals is ensured by diagnostic goal setting and efficacy (as indicators of technology); a collection of qualities, projectability, algorithmizability, systematicity, and controllability, represent different facets of the repeatability of educational technologies [11-15].

The teacher's technological proficiency

It is evident that a modern teacher must both grasp the system of technological knowledge and conceptually understand his own educational activities in order to successfully implement actions linked to the introduction of pedagogical technologies. As a technologist, a teacher can also be a researcher, organizer, mentor, consultant, practical psychologist, designer, methodologist, or didactician. Essential traits like knowledge, didactic self-awareness, intellectual activity, openness to new ideas, critical thinking, and a communication-oriented culture should all be present in his personality.

Bibliography

1. Djakhonobodkhonovna, K. G. (2019). Problems encountered in teaching English as a foreign language. *Вопросы науки и образования*, (5 (50)), 165-167.
2. Ходжаева, Г. Д. (2019). Использование коммуникативного подхода в обучении грамматике английского языка. *Проблемы современной науки и образования*, (12-2 (145)), 153-155.
3. Rakhmanov, D. M., Khodjaeva, G. D., & Mamaruziev, S. (2023). Ancient greek architecture. *American Journal of Technology and Applied Sciences*, 18, 71-75.
4. Khodjaeva, G. D. (2022). Actual problems of teaching a foreign language in secondary schools. *Экономика и социум*, (12-1 (103)), 145-148.
5. Ходжаева, Г. Д. (2021). Формирование Навыков Осознания Гражданских Прав И Обязанностей У Молодежи В Современном Обществе. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 2(12), 189-192.
6. Djakhonobodovna, K. G., Nazirovich, A. U., & Yigitalievna, K. M. (2019). Innovative assessment of students' experience in higher educational institutions. *Вестник науки и образования*, (19-3 (73)), 46-48.

7. Abdukadirov, U. N. (2022). Best practice of motivating speaking activities for lower levels. Экономика и социум, (12-1 (103)), 24-27.
8. Nazirovich, A. U. (2023). Modern methods of teaching english in higher education. Образование наука и инновационные идеи в мире, 20(2), 45-47.
9. Nazirovich, A. U. (2023). Features of the translation of technical texts. Academia Science Repository, 4(05), 58-63.
10. Baykuzieva, G. A. (2020). Problems of Development of Fruit and Vegetable Industry in Fergana Region and Their Solutions. International Scientific Journal Theoretical & Applied Science, 10(90), 78-82.
11. Nazirovich, A. U. (2022). Turizmga oid atamalarning lingvokulturologik xususiyatlari. Conferencea, 256-258.
12. Abdukodirov, U. N. (2020). Using of dictionary sources for improving integrated teaching methods. Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology, 2(11), 230-234.
13. Abdukodirov, U. (2020). Materials development in teaching. In МИРОВАЯ НАУКА 2020. Проблемы и перспективы (pp. 3-5).
14. Gulhumor S. Kahhorova. (2022). The notions of wael hallaq on an introduction to islamic law. American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research, 2(06), 63–67. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume02Issue06-12>
15. Kizi, K. G. S. (2023). A deep study of wael B hallaq’s explaining views of islamic law. Asian Journal Of Multidimensional Research, 12(8), 7-10.

Research Science and Innovation House